

Synthesis of some New Benzopyranopyridazin-3-ones

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Several benzopyran derivatives possess various biological activities¹. In view of pesticidal properties² of hydrazides and other nitrogen heterocycles, it was considered worthwhile to synthesise various benzopyran derivatives having fused heterocyclic moiety.

The methodology adopted for the synthesis of the desired compounds involved the reaction of substituted phenol with 3-chloropropionic acid in presence of alkali to give 3-(*p*-methylphenoxy)propionic acid (2), which when cyclised by PPA gave 6-methyl-2,3-dihydrobenzopyran-4-one (3) (Scheme 1). The formation of 3 was evidenced by the disappearance of OH band in ir spectrum and a singlet at δ 11.5 in pmr spectrum. Compound 3 was further converted into 4 by reacting it with methylchloroacetate in benzene using NaH as a base. The formation of 4 was established by appearance of ester C=O band at 1750 cm^{-1} in ir spectrum and OCH₂ singlet at δ 3.8 in pmr spectrum. Compound 4 when reacted with various hydrazides

in methanol furnished *N*²-substituted-benzopyranopyridazinones (5). The formation of 5 was confirmed by disappearance of ester C=O band and appearance of two amide C=O bands at 1685 and 1665 cm^{-1} in ir spectrum.

Experimental

Melting points were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-437 spectrometer and pmr spectra on a Perkin-Elmer R-32 spectrometer using TMS as an internal standard. The purity of the compounds (Table 1) in addition to elemental analysis was checked by tlc.

6-Methyl-2,3-dihydrobenzopyran-4-one (3): 3-(4-Methylphenoxy)propionic acid (2; 0.01 mol) was added to a stirred solution of orthophosphoric acid (10 ml) containing P₂O₅ (10 g). The mixture was heated at 80° for 2 h on a steam-bath, then cooled

Scheme 1

TABLE I—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS 5a—q*

Compd. no.	R	M p. °C	Yield %
5a	<i>p</i> -CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ -	180	68.10
b	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ -	196	61.70
c	<i>p</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ -	82	74.60
d	4-Cl-5-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ OCH ₂ -	170	81.30
e	<i>p</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -OCH(CH ₃)-	188	53.00
f	<i>o</i> -NO ₂ -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ -	88	64.30
g	<i>m</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -OCH ₂ -	110	57.10
h	C ₆ H ₅ -OCH(CH ₃)-	142	60.30
i	<i>o</i> -CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ OCH ₂ -	117	58.20
j	<i>p</i> -OCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	160	68.80
k	<i>o</i> -OCOCH ₃ -C ₆ H ₄ -	101	64.20
l	<i>o</i> -Cl-C ₆ H ₄ -	168	55.20
m	2-OH,3-Cl-C ₆ H ₃ -	247	68.00
n	3,5-(NO ₂) ₂ -C ₆ H ₃ -	251	79.30
o	2-CH(CH ₃) ₂ ,5-CH ₃ -C ₆ H ₃ -OCH ₂ -	182	67.20
p	C ₆ H ₅ CH ₂ -	132	52.10
q	C ₆ H ₅ -CH=CH-	87	58.70

*All compounds gave satisfactory C, H, N elemental analyses.

and poured in ice-cold water (200 ml). It was neutralised with sodium carbonate to give brown coloured gummy mass which was extracted in chloroform and the solvent was removed under reduced pressure. The solid obtained was recrystallised from ethanol, m.p. 69°; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1700, 1600 and 1060 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.3 (3H, s, ArCH₃), 2.6 (2H, t, CH₂CO), 4.2 (2H, t, OCH₂) and 6.9–7.3 (3H, m, ArH).

3-Carbomethoxymethyl-6-methylbenzopyran-4-one (4): To compound 3 (20 mmol) in dry benzene (30 ml) sodium hydride (1 g) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 h. Methylchloroacetate (40 mmol) was added to it and refluxed for 6 h, then cooled and washed with ice-water (1 × 10 ml). The separated organic layer was evaporated under reduced pressure and viscous gummy liquid obtained was purified by column chromatography (benzene-chloroform, 95 : 5, v/v), b.p. 200° at 100 mm; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1760, 1700 and 1060 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.3 (3H, s, Ar-CH₃), 2.6–3.5 (3H, m, -CH₂C and CHCH₂), 3.8 (3H, s, OCH₃), 4.6 (2H, d, OCH₂) and 6.9–7.3 (3H, m, ArH).

2-(*p*-Methylphenoxy)-9-methylbenzopyrano [3,4-*c*]pyridazin-3-one (5a): A mixture of 4 (100 mmol) and *p*-methylphenoxyacetic acid hydrazide (100 mmol) in methanol (125 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h, then cooled and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The residue was treated with ice-water (200 ml) and the solid obtained was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 180° (Found : C, 69.10 ; H, 5.40 ; N, 7.60. C₂₁H₂₀N₂O₄ requires : C, 69.12 ; H, 5.41 ; N, 7.69%); ν_{\max} (KBr) 1685, 1660 and 1620 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl₃) 2.5 (6H, s, 2 × ArCH₃), 3.5 (1H, m, CH), 4.4 (2H, d, OCH₂-CH), 4.6 (2H, s, OCH₂) and 6.9–7.7 (7H, m, ArH).

References

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